

Long-run and Short-run Effects of Foreign Trade and Foreign Direct Investment on Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author FHF designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors OA and GCA managed the analyses of the study. Author OA managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/AJEBA/2017/33065

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Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19634>

Original Research Article

Received 29th March 2017
Accepted 14th June 2017
Published 21st June 2017

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to assess the impact of Foreign Trade and Foreign Direct Investment on Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1980-2014. Inferential statistics were used for the analysis. Using Augmented Dickey Fuller test, the results shows that all variables were stationary in their first difference and that necessitated the application of Johansen co-integration test. The trace statistics of 59.28557 and maximum Eigen statistics of 32.58741 were greater than the critical values of 47.85613 and 27.58434 at 5% level of significance respectively. Both trace and maximum Eigen value indicates one co-integration equation. Further investigations based on Johansen co-integration test, indicate that long run equilibrium relationship exist among the variables of interest. The long run result shows a positive coefficient of 5.61 and 0.23 for Foreign Direct Investment and non oil export at 1% level of probability respectively. On the other hand, the coefficient of non oil import in the long run was negative (0.015) and significant at 1% level of probability. The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) results show that there is no short run effect of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on agricultural productivity. It was

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recommended that importation should be discouraged, especially goods that the nation can produce or goods that the nation has comparative advantage in the production; Non oil goods exportation should be encourage through favorable trade policies, boosting the production of local industries and improving on the quality of Nigeria goods so as to compete favorably in the world market.

Keywords: Foreign trade; foreign direct investment; export; import and agricultural productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural productivity is referred to as the output produced by a given level of input in Agricultural sector or it is a measure of the ratio of agricultural output to agricultural inputs. [1], viewed rising agricultural productivity as the most important tool of successful industrialization while decline or stagnation in agricultural productivity is the principal explanation for poor economic performance.

[2] viewed foreign trade (FT) as trade between two or more countries in which each other obtain things that are of better quality or less expensive or simply different from the goods and services produced in their country. Foreign trade is the backbone of growth and development of every country of the world. As pointed out by [3] foreign trade has been identified as an instrument and driver of economic growth. This is so because trade enhances the efficient production of goods and services through allocation of resources to countries that have comparative advantage in their production. In addition, its impact on a country's economy is not limited to the quantitative gains, but also structural changes in the economy and facilitates the international capital flow. [4], stated that international trade brings welfare and efficiency gains to all countries irrespective of their initial conditions, level of development, technological abilities and natural resources endowment. [5] added that foreign trade has been and is today an economic force that has spurred agriculture, commerce, technology growth, spread cultural patterns and stimulate exploration and colonization.

[6], defined foreign direct investment (FDI) as an investment undertaken by an enterprise that is either wholly or partly foreign-owned. FDI is also viewed as a form of lending or finance in the area of equity participation which involves the transfer of resources such as capital, technology, management and marketing expertise to the receiving country in other to boost existing production capabilities [7].

Attempt in attracting FDI into Nigeria have been based on the need to maximize it potential benefits. The Nigerian government had in the past endeavored to provide foreign investors with a healthy environment in form of low corporate and income tax rates, tax holidays, other types of tax concessions, preferential tariffs, special economic zones, investment financial subsidies, soft loan or loan guarantees, free land or land subsidies, relocation and expatriation subsidies, job training and employment subsidies, infrastructure subsidies, research and development support and derogation from regulations, usually for very large projects. In spite of the blessed enormous human and natural resources and other incentives, Nigeria in the last few years receives low proportion of global FDI inflow. This is because Nigeria is viewed by the foreign investors as a high risk market for investment [8].

Despite the dwindling nature of crude oil price in the world market, discovering of crude oil by other countries which leads to increase in competition, substitute for some crude oil product and other benefits of agricultural export, there is no significant shift from oil non oil export. [9], reported that shortly after the independence, the non oil export contributed over 90 percent to the Gross Domestic product (GDP), but continue to decline drastically from mid 70s' to a single digit (3.1%) in 1980s'. [10], reported that agricultural sector which has been relatively stagnant at 3% growth performance, moved from 4.1% growth rate in 1998 to 7.4% by end of 2009. This was as a result of a renewed attention of government within the period through various reforms programmes that also encouraged increasing private sector entrepreneurial activities. [11] also pointed out that because of the persistent political and institutional instability, unstable macro-economic policies, bad governance and uncertainty, international confidence in Nigeria was badly affected, thereby affecting the flow of foreign investors into the country.

The broad objective of this study is to assess the impact of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on agricultural productivity in Nigeria from 1980 to 2014. Specifically the study intended to:

- i. Examine the long run effect of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on agricultural productivity;
- ii. Examine the short run effect of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on agricultural productivity;

Based on the specific objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis was tested:

Ho₁: Foreign trade and foreign direct investment have no significant effect on agricultural productivity in the long run.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 The Study Area

The study was conducted in Nigeria. Nigeria is located in the western part of Africa between Latitude 5° and 15° North and longitude 3° and 15° East of the meridian. Nigeria has a total area of 923, 768 square kilometers with land occupying 910, 768 square kilometers and water occupying about 13,000 square kilometers. The country is bounded in the north by republic of Niger and Chad, in the south by the Atlantic Ocean, in the west and east by the republic of Benin and Cameroon respectively [12].

2.2 Method of Data Collection

The data for this study were collected from world development index. The data were basically annual time series data from 1980 to 2014.

2.3 Techniques of Data Analysis

Using Augmented Dickey fuller (ADF), an analysis of the unit root test properties of the variables collected was carried out to avoid spurious results. The Johansen co-integration test was used to determine long run relationship among the variables. The vector error correction model (VECM) was used to analyze objective I and II, since the Johansen co-integration test indicates that one co-integration equation exist among variables. The t-test from vector error correction model estimations was used to test the hypothesis.

2.4 Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey fuller (ADF) was used to test for the presence of unit root. The model of the ADF test with a constant and trend was specified below:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_2 t + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_2 \Delta Y_{t-i} + e_t$$

Where:

Y_t = Current value of agricultural productivity or foreign trade or foreign direct investment.

Y_{t-i} = Immediate past values of agricultural productivity or foreign trade or foreign direct investment.

t = Variable time

Δ = Change operator

p = Optimal lag length

α_0 = Constant

2.5 Johansen Co-integration Test

The Johansen co-integration equation was used to test for the long run relationship among the variables

$$\Delta Y_t = \Pi Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \beta x_t + e_t$$

Where;

ΔY_t = first difference of a (n x i) Vector of the variables of interest.

Π = (n x n) coefficient matrix associated with lagged values of the endogenous variables

Y_{t-1} = Lag values of Y_t

Γ_i = (n x (k - 1) matrix of short term coefficients

βx = Co-integrating vector

e_t = (n x 1) vector of white Noise Residual

2.6 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

To estimate the long run and short run relationship between the variables since co-integration exist, the model was specified below:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln AGP_t = & \alpha_0 + i - 3P\alpha_1 \Delta \ln EXP_{t-3} \\ & + i - 3P\alpha_2 \Delta \ln FDI_{t-3} + i - 3P\alpha_3 \Delta \ln BTA_{t-3} + \\ & \sum_{i=3}^p \alpha_4 \Delta \ln AGL_{t-3} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_5 \Delta \ln EXR_{t-3} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_6 \Delta \ln INTR_{t-3} + \\ & \sum_{i=3}^p \alpha_7 \Delta \ln IMP_{t-3} + \alpha_8 ECT_{t-3} + u_t \end{aligned}$$

Where;

α_0 = Constant; $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_8$ = Coefficients, EXR = Exchange rate, EXP = Export, IMP = Import, INTR = Interest rate, BTA = Budget to Agricultural, AGL = Agricultural loan, ECT = Error correction term
 AGP = Agricultural Productivity, FDI = Foreign Direct Investment
 U_t = Error term, \ln = Natural log, Δ = Change operator, p = optimal lag length

variables were not stationary at level, but became stationary at first difference order 1, 1(1). This implies that the application of Johansen co-integration became necessary to determine the long run relationship among variables since most of the variables contain non stationary time trend.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) test was employed to test for the presence of unit root. Table 1 shows the unit root test result for Agricultural Productivity (AGP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Non oil Trade (import and export), Exchange rate (EXR), Interest rate (INR), Budget to agricultural sector (BTA) and agricultural loan (AL). The ADF test result indicates that only the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) variable was found to be stationary at level and at first difference order 1, 1(1), while other

3.2 Johansen Co-integration Test

Further investigation was carried out on the series properties of the order 1(1) variables through the use of Johansen co-integration test. The co-integration test results are presented in Tables 2 and 3 for trace and maximum Eigen statistics respectively. Thus, based on the decision rule, the trace statistics of 59.28557 and maximum Eigen statistics of 32.58741 were greater than the critical values of 47.85613 and 27.58434 at 5% level of significance respectively. Both trace and maximum Eigen value indicate 1 co-integration equation at 5% level of significance. On this basis, the null hypothesis of no co-integration relationship among agricultural productivity, Foreign Direct Investment, Non oil trade (import and export), Exchange rate, interest rate, budget to agricultural sector and agricultural loan is rejected.

Table 1. Unit root test

Variables	Level		First difference	
	t. statistics	Probability values	t. statistics	Probability values
AGP	-2.139491 (-2.957110)	0.2314	-2.812040* (-2.617434)	0.0678
FDI	-3.096579* (-2.963972)	0.0376	-7.137748*** (-2.615817)	0.0000
IMP	2.446216 (-2.951125)	1.0000	-4.593960*** (-3.646342)	0.0000
EXP	-1.312015 (-1.951000)	0.1715	-11.57378*** (-2.636901)	0.0000
EXR	1.323431 (-1.951000)	0.9502	-4.931352*** (-2.636901)	0.0000
INTR	-0.196403 (-1.951000)	0.6081	-6.473197*** (-2.636901)	0.0000
BTA	0.253539 (-1.951687)	0.7534	-8.420234*** (-2.639210)	0.0000
AGL	7.304089 (-2.951125)	1.0000	-5.657803*** (-3.646342)	0.0000

Note * ** *** denote rejection of null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significant level respectively. Base on Mackinnon (1996) one sided P-values. t-critical value of the corresponding t. statistics are given in parenthesis. AGP=Agricultural Productivity; FDI=Foreign Direct Investment; IMP=Non Oil Import; EXP=Non Oil Export; EXR=Exchange Rate; INTR=Interest Rate; BTA=Budget to Agriculture; AGL=Agricultural Loan
 Source: Author's computation from E-views, 2017

Table 2. Co-integration rank test (Trace)

Hypothesized no. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace statistics	0.05 critical value	Probability **
None*	0.650484	59.28557**	47.85613	0.0030
At most 1	0.426256	26.69816	29.79707	0.1092
At most 2	0.262587	9.475402	15.49471	0.3232
At most 3	0.001050	0.032567	3.841466	0.8567

Note ** denote rejection of null hypothesis at 5% significant level based on Mackinno (1999) critical value.
Source: Author's computation from E-views, 2017

Table 3. Co-integration rank test (Maximum Eigen value)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Max-Eigen statistics	0.05 critical value	Probability **
None*	0.650484	32.58741**	27.58434	0.0104
At most 1	0.426256	17.22276	21.13162	0.1617
At most 2	0.262587	9.442835	14.26460	0.2512
At most 3	0.001050	0.032567	3.841466	0.8567

Note ** denote rejection of null hypothesis at 5% significant level based on Mackinno (1999) critical value.
Source: Author's computation from E-views, 2017

3.3 Long-run Impact of Foreign Direct Investment and Non Oil Trade on Agricultural Productivity

The application of ECM was necessary because of the existence of co-integration among the variables. The result of the ECM is presented in the upper part of Table 4. The result shows that in the long-run, the coefficient of the foreign direct investment (FDI) is positive (5.61) and significant at 1%. This implies that a unit increase in foreign direct investment will result in 5.61 unit increase in Agricultural Productivity. This result agrees with the findings of [13] who examine the sustainability of the FDI-growth relationship in Nigeria, using the Johansen co-integration framework and a multivariate VAR within a vector error correction model, found the evidence of a long run equilibrium relationship between FDI inflow and economic growth. This result meets the theoretical expectation which may be associated with increase in job opportunity, increase in other local business and availability of other social amenities such as road network, education that is being provided by the foreign industries.

The coefficient of non oil import is negative (-0.01474) and significant at 1%. This implies that a unit increase in the importation of non oil goods will lead to decrease in the Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria by 0.015. This finding correspond with the findings of [14] which find out that a unit increase in import in Nigeria, led to 1.72% decrease in real GDP. This also implies that a long run relationship exist between foreign

trade and Nigeria economy. This result is contrary to a priori expectation and may be explain by the suspension of local production in Nigeria.

The coefficient of non oil export is positive and significant at 1%. This implies that a unit increase in non oil export will result in an increase of 0.23 units in agricultural productivity. This is also in line with the findings of [15] which reveal that there is a very weak and infinitesimal impact of non oil export in influencing rate of change in level of economic growth in Nigeria. This result agrees with the theoretical expectation and this may be associated with the market for agricultural products.

The short run Error Correction Model (ECM) result for the impact of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on agricultural productivity is presented in the lower part of Table 4. The ECT is -0.01462 which indicates a low speed of adjustment of variables towards equilibrium. This implies that the speed of adjustment where the Foreign Trade and Foreign Direct Investment will equilibrate Agricultural Productivity is 0.014626.

The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.6626 indicating that 66% of the variation in agricultural productivity is attributed to the variables included in the VECM while the remaining 34% are other variables that were not included in the model. The short run error correction results reveal that there is no short run effect of Foreign Trade and Foreign Direct Investment on Agricultural

Table 4. Vector error correction estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t-statistics	
Long-run				
AGP (-1)	1.0000	-	-	
FDI (-1)	5.61E-05***	7.1E-10	7.85590	
IMP (-1)	-0.014374***	0.00211	-6.81197	
EXP (-1)	0.063549***	0.01149	5.53228	
Constant	0.673272	-	-	
Short-run				
ECT	AGP	FDI	IMP	EXP
CointEq1	-0.014626 (0.01694) [-0.86324]	-2.04E+08 (1.3E+08) [-1.56486]	33.15318 (42.1365) [0.78680]	-5.709888 (10.2463) [-0.55726]
AGP(-1)	-0.511630 (0.42253) [-1.21088]	-4.77E+08 (3.2E+09) [-0.14693]	-1830.287 (1050.81) [-1.74179]	-477.7704* (255.525) [-1.86976]
AGP(-2)	0.404932 (0.32763) [1.123596]	2.76E+09 (2.5E+09) [1.09616]	209.8972 (814.792) [0.25761]	-89.80960 (198.132) [-0.45328]
AGP(-3)	-0.361531 (0.42484) [-0.850971]	7.06E+08 (3.3E-09) [0.21611]	-2358.718** (1056.57) [-2.23243]	-542.3742** (256.926) [-2.11102]
FDI(-1)	3.90E-11 (6.3E-11) [0.61466]	0.501136 (0.48750) [1.02798]	1.36E-07 (1.6E-07) [0.86557]	5.53E-08 (3.8E-08) [1.44238]
FDI(-2)	4.47E-11 (5.0E-11) [0.88671]	0.715645* (0.38730) [1.84780]	3.33E-07*** (1.3E-07) [2.65977]	1.15E-07*** (3.0E-08) [3.76557]
FDI(-3)	-1.17E-11 (4.9E-11) [-0.23772]	0.460152 (0.37687) [1.22098]	1.19E-07 (1.2E-07) [0.97550]	7.10E-08** (3.0E-08) [2.39376]
IMP(-1)	-0.000261 (0.0019) [-1.39596]	-1814187. (1439730) [-1.26009]	-0.574196 (0.46568) [-1.23302]	0.025602 (0.11324) [0.22609]
IMP(-2)	-0.000121 (0.00024) [0.49493]	-804607.1 (1872433) [-0.42971]	-0.604633 (0.60564) [-0.99834]	-0.227515 (0.14727) [-1.54485]
IMP(-3)	4.38E-05 (0.00023) [0.19167]	1268279. (1758582) [0.72119]	-0.014950 (056882) [-0.02628]	-0.197854 (0.13832) [-1.43043]
EXP(-1)	0.001334 (0.00102) [1.31077]	12939828 (7823490) [1.65397]	0.241665 (2.53052) [0.09550]	-0.343458 (0.61534) [-0.55816]
EXP(-2)	0.000808 (0.00140) [0.57652]	11396033 (1.1E+07) [1.05803]	-2.576908 (3.48390) [-0.73966]	0.231170 (0.84718) [0.227287]
EXP(-3)	0.001130 (0.00120) [0.94035]	-550655 (9242758) [-0.59513]	4.58952 (2.98958) [1.49150]	0.741011 (0.72697) [1.01931]
Constant	0.032227 (0.09276) [0.34742]	5.35E+08 (7.1E+08) [0.74957]	-138.4194 (230.698) [-0.60000]	-34.14845 (56.0986) [-0.60872]
R-squared	0.662619	0.834451	0.932189	0.977658
Adj. R-square	0.221428	0.617964	0.843512	0.948442
F. statistic	1.501887	3.854512	10.51227	33.46270
AIC	-1.560108	43.96596	14.07753	11.24953
SC	0.727470	44.79860	14.91016	11.24953

Note *** (**) (*) denote rejection of null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significant level respectively. AGP=Agricultural Productivity; FDI=Foreign Direct Investment; IMP=Non Oil Import; EXP=Non Oil Export; EXR=Exchange Rate; INTR=Interest Rate; BTA=Budget to Agriculture; AGL=Agricultural Loan; AIC=Akaike information criterion SC=Schwarz criterion,
Source: Author's computation from E-views, 2017

Productivity. This result is consistent with the relationship between foreign direct investment in findings of [16] who examine the causal agriculture and agricultural output in Nigeria,

found that no short run influence from FDI in agriculture to agricultural output. This is possible because of the frequent change in regimes and policies.

3.4 Test of Hypothesis

The standard error of foreign direct investment non oil import and non oil export are;

7.1E-10, 0.00211 and 0.01149 respectively.

3.5 Decision Rule

If: $SE(\alpha_1) > \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1$, Accept H0 and Reject H1

If: $SE(\alpha_1) < \frac{1}{2} \alpha_1$, Accept H1 and Reject H0

H0 implies that at the specified level of significance the effect associated independent variable on the dependent variable is not statistically significant at the specified level of significance.

H1 implies that the parameter estimate is statistically significant at the specified significant level.

$SE(\alpha_1) = 7.1E-10 < \frac{1}{2} 5.61E-5$ i.e. accept H1 and reject H0.

$SE(\alpha_2) = 0.00211 < \frac{1}{2} 0.01437$ i.e. accept H1 and reject H0.

$SE(\alpha_3) = 0.01149 < \frac{1}{2} 0.63549$ i.e. accept H1 and reject H0.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the results revealed that in the long run, the coefficient of foreign direct investment and non oil export were positive and significant at 1% while the coefficient of non oil import was negative and significant at 1%. The result also showed that non-oil import, non-oil export and foreign direct investment has no short run significant effect on the agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government should discourage non-oil importation, especially goods that the nation can produce or goods that the nation has comparative advantage in the production.

2. Non oil goods exportation should be encouraged, by boosting the production of local industries, improving the quality of Nigerian goods so as to compete favorably in the world market.
3. Policies that will encourage non oil exportation should be put in place.
4. Conditions that will encourage both foreign and home investors to invest in diverse sector of the economy should be put in place.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Peer-review history:
The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/19634>